

Derivatization of Amines as Benzylthiuronium Dithiocarbamates

N. N. Singh and K. S. Boparai

A convenient procedure for the derivatization of primary and secondary amines, as benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates, is described. Eighteen amines have been derivatized. The derivatives are readily purified and thus useful for characterization.

Amines can be derivatized as amides formed by the reaction with acyl or aroyl halides, as thioureas formed with isothiocyanates, or as salts with acids. The derivatives commonly recommended are benzamides¹, benzenesulphonamides¹, phenylthioureas^{2,3} and quaternary ammonium salts⁴. It has been found that primary and secondary aliphatic amines and some aromatic amines can be more conveniently derivatized as benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates, the ease of derivatization depending on the basic strength of the amine. The

R₁ = alkyl or aryl group

R₂ = H or alkyl group

reactions involved are rapid, the formation of dithiocarbamates in the case of strong bases being exothermic. The derivatives are obtained in good yield and are readily purified. The reagents employed are readily available in pure form. In view of this, the procedure is recommended for the characterization of amines. A heterogeneous group of eighteen amines has been derivatized. Corrected m.p.'s of the derivatives have been recorded in Table I. The sulphur and nitrogen content of the derivatives, as determined by Messinger's method and micro Dumas method respectively, agrees well with the calculated values.

Methyl, ethyl and propyl amines required for derivatization were prepared by Hofmann reaction⁵. Attempts were made to derivatize various other available amines. The derivatization of nitroanilines, *o*- and *p*-anisidines, aminophenols, *p*-phenylenediamine, *l*-amino anthraquinone, monoethanolamine and glycine was unsatisfactory. The derivatives obtained

1. R. Sasin *et al.*, *J. Am. Oil Chemists's Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 358.
2. F. C. Whitmore and T. Otterbacher, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 1909.
3. E. L. Brown and N. Campbell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1699.
4. N. D. Cheronis and J. B. Entrikin, "Identification of Organic Compounds", A Student's Text Using Semimicro Techniques, Interscience Publishers, 1963, p. 276.
5. A. I. Vogel, "A Text-Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1956, p. 413.

in the case of ethylenediamine and hydrazine hydrate were highly unstable and underwent hydrolytic decomposition rapidly. As observed in the case of benzylthiuronium carboxylates^{6,7}, the benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates have a slight tendency to undergo hydrolytic decomposition in the aqueous medium, due to the instability of benzyliothiourea. The dithiocarbamates are best prepared in alcohol.

EXPERIMENTAL

In a 25 ml. conical flask, 1 ml. of pure carbon disulphide, and 10 drops of concentrated aqueous ammonia were placed, 1 ml. of an amine was slowly run in with shaking (in the case of a solid amine 1 g. of finely powdered amine was added). The contents of the flask were swirled vigorously for 10 minutes. Required volume of ethanol was then introduced in order to obtain a clear solution, facilitated by warming, if necessary. The contents were further swirled for about 10 minutes. The pH of the solution was adjusted between 7 and 8 by the dropwise addition of *N* HCl in the beginning and 0.1 *N* HCl towards the end, using phenolphthalein as indicator or with the help of universal pH paper (E. Merck), if the phenolphthalein indicator was unsatisfactory due to the dark brown colour of the solution particularly in the case of aromatic amines. To the ammonium dithiocarbamate solution thus obtained, 1 g. of benzylthiuronium chloride dissolved in 3 ml. of ethanol was added dropwise with shaking. Benzylthiuronium dithiocarbamates were precipitated immediately in most cases, however, chilling was necessary in a few cases. The precipitate was filtered at the pump and rinsed with a little cold alcohol. In some cases the derivatives were found to be analytically pure, and in the case of others one or two crystallizations from ethanol afforded pure product. The derivatives were dried in a vacuum desiccator and their m.p.'s were determined by the capillary tube method. Corrected m.p.'s and the analysis of the derivatives are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Benzylthiuronium Salts of Dithiocarbamic acids obtained from various Amines

No.	Amine	Cor., m.p. of salts	% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
			Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
1.	Methylamine	110	35.18	35.65	15.37	15.52
2.	Dimethylamine	91	33.47	33.93	14.62	14.43
3.	Ethylamine	107	33.47	33.50	14.62	14.51
4.	Propylamine	102	31.91	32.05	13.94	13.98
5.	<i>n</i> -Butylamine	98	30.49	30.00	13.32	12.94
6.	<i>iso</i> -Butylamine	104	30.49	29.90	13.32	13.63
7.	Cyclohexylamine	117	28.17	28.00	12.30	12.12
8.	Piperidine	103	29.37	29.50	12.83	12.26
9.	Benzylamine	108	27.53	27.93	12.02	12.25
10.	Phenylhydrazine	119	27.44	27.63	15.98	15.77
11.	Aniline	149	28.67	28.15	12.53	12.95
12.	<i>N</i> -Methylaniline	91	27.53	27.64	12.02	12.00
13.	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	171	26.00	26.35	11.36	11.75
14.	<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	183	23.21	23.05	10.14	10.25
15.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine	159	27.53	27.13	12.02	12.03
16.	<i>p</i> -Toluidine	178	27.53	27.74	12.02	12.40
17.	α -Naphthylamine	195	24.95	24.60	10.90	11.23
18.	Benzidine	290-299d	28.75	28.65	12.56	12.42

d = decomposition.

School of Studies in Chemistry,
Vikram University,
Ujjain.

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6. J. J. Donleavy, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1004.
7. W. A. Bouner, *ibid.*, 1948, **70**, 3508.